

Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Work Family Conflict Among Female Teachers

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Abstract

Work Family refers to the situation where all family members do jobs or work. Work family is controversial, and conflicts arise. Work Family Conflict describes the conflict between work and family domains. The present research explored the relationship between job satisfaction and work family conflict among female teachers. A sample consisting of 300 female teachers (all married) was taken from the educational institution of Islamabad and Rawalpindi. Two scales were administered on the sample. It was hypothesized that teachers who have nuclear family systems have less family conflict than those who have joint Family systems. Another aim was to determine the status of job of female teachers (permanent and non-permanent) and data was also analyzed with respect to demographic variables. The findings of the study indicate that working women with children have less job satisfaction and have more problems in work family conflict. Moreover, working married women who have nuclear family system have more job satisfaction than the women having joint family system and thus face more difficulties in work and family.

Keywords: job satisfaction, family conflict, performance

1. Introduction

The term "job satisfaction" refers to the teachers' level of contentment with their work as educators and their perception of the connection between what they want and what they get from their jobs. The most imperative issue for the researchers throughout the way of the research has been job satisfaction. Satisfied educators are continuously able to invest additional energy to team up with students and guardians to make progress. Saif et al., (2016) uncovered that significant variables like employer stability, cooperation in direction, holidays facilities, top administration's mentality, pay increments, family-explicit time, promotion and development opportunities, and adaptable working hours, in addition to other things, all affect female representatives' degrees of occupation fulfillment. Nasir et al. (2011) claimed that teachers' work execution and job satisfaction are inextricably linked. It appears that a stronger positive correlation exists between professional behavior and job satisfaction. In the present business economies, "Work-Family conflict (WFC)" is the trendy expression for circumstances where in it is hard for a person to adjust the requests of both work and day to day life. WFC is a current topic right now (Burke & El-Kot, 2010), and researchers studying employees' perspectives on work and the workplace are especially interested in it.

Work-family conflicts are included in inter-role conflicts. Such types of conflicts between roles are caused by hasty shifts at work, which require employees to show his or her performance with an improved level and be more committed to the job and organization. The conflict has three dimensions, which may lead the organization to expect employees to stay on duty station for more than specified in normal routine in that organization and give more preference to the official tasks than any other personal need required by themselves or any family members at home, even at the cost of their independent personal life. Time-based conflict in one of the major type of above mentioned conflicts and can be referred as first type. Such type of conflict takes place when one job portfolio requires more time than the other duties. Marital status, family size, the number of children and dependent parents, and a lack of social support from the society to do job as female members of the community all affect the amount of time spent at home. Working hours, commuting time, shift time, and overtime are all examples of work time. Time invested at home is energy spent doing family tasks. Stress-based conflicts are the second type of conflicts that happens caused in finishing the work of one domain impacts the other work. Last but not least, when performance in two domains is not compatible, behavior-based conflict occurs. For example, expressiveness, being personal, and awareness are viewed as useless in the work environment however characteristics for the family.

The representatives who have family responsibilities may view flexible working hours as a part of their mental agreement. This allows them to see a balance between activities that are fun and serious. Overseeing work-family requests has become a difficult task for representatives and associations in virtually every country. As a result of a development in the organization, important entryways for women the issue of work family battle is extended and ended up being more huge. In the cutting edge period, it is apparent that it is connected to shifts in efficiency, family work, an expansion in advanced education, and the developing pattern toward female support. When juggling responsibilities at home and at work, working women frequently experience stress (Shockley et al., 2017). It has become an established issue that Work Family Conflict represents a collectivist culture in Pakistan. Thus, this conflict terribly affects Pakistan's female labor force.

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Over the past few decades, the number of working women and profitable employment has increased. However, this trend has not been accompanied by a similar increase in men's contribution to unpaid homework, men's entry into traditionally female-dominated occupations, or significant policy changes at the federal, state, or local level. The term work-family conflict is often used to describe the tension between work or career and family responsibilities. Work-family conflict is said to be a kind of conflict where work pressure and family support are more or less mutually exclusive. According to Eynde, Claessens, and Mortelmans (2020), the term 'work-family conflict' refers to the difficulties associated with reconciling work and family life. Conflicts between work and home are deeply rooted in the social changes brought about by women's greater participation in the labor market. Work-family conflicts cause many long-term problems (Ilies, Huth, Ryan & Dimotakis, 2015; Ali, 2022). Several studies examining the association between work-family conflict and job satisfaction have found a negative association (Purwanto, 2020; Ali, 2022). However, there are limited data on how conflict affects satisfaction, and the correlation of this data precludes causal conclusions. Role theory and ecosystem theory are two important theoretical views that have guided research on the interactions between work and family (Mullen, Kelley & Kelloway, 2008; Ali, 2022). Various variables affect the interaction between work and personal life. Some researchers have emphasized the importance of identifying the role of cognitive variables in work-family interactions (Janasz & Behson, 2007; Van Steenbergen & Ellemers, 2009; Poposki, 2011; Ali, 2015; Ali and Rehman, 2015; Ali, 2018; Ali and Ahmad, 2016; Ali and Audi, 2018; Ali and Bibi, 2017; Ali and Senturk, 2019). The negative effects of work-family conflict have been identified as follows, but when happiness is low and stress levels are high, specific emotional and behavioral outcomes are determined not only by the situation and stressors, but also by increase. There are theoretical models that suggest that they are mediated by individual perceptions, beliefs and insights (Oblenovic, Jianguo, Kudaikurov, Khan, 2020). The happy moments that people experience in their work or occupation are called "work satisfaction." A person's job satisfaction increases with happiness. To improve productivity and job satisfaction: reengineering, job expansion, job enrichment. Leadership style and culture, employee engagement and job satisfaction are also factors that can affect job satisfaction. Despite the obvious associations, job satisfaction is not the same as motivation or attitude. Job design goals, autonomy in professional life, and reputation (Shaukat, Vishnumolakala, Al Bustami, 2019). Organizations around the world are looking to this trait because it has a direct impact on overall retention rates. Employee reaction to work is measured using the most commonly used rating scales. This is similar to a paper-based or PC-based survey that captures different aspects of job fulfillment and creates a temporary source of information for business planning. This research can give a base to additional investigations in the field of work related hardships for wedded ladies existing in Pakistan culture (Saher, Matloob, Tahreen, Ali and Al Sulim, 2013). Numerous studies have been conducted in Pakistan, where work-life conflict has also emerged, according to the study. In any case, no exploration has solely centered around work-family struggle looked by wedded working ladies and their refereeing style from individual worth and responsibility point of view. Additionally, the research will be useful. Women in Pakistan who are employed must confront the issue because our society is dominated by men. They are expected to carry out all responsibilities at home and at work if they are employed. Pakistan having an Islamic culture and with conventional society, ladies are supposed to remain at homes and perform tasks at homes. Their doing job does not conflict with the values. The purpose of the study, in context of Pakistan is that the phenomenon of job satisfaction and related scales need a great deal of studies.

1.1. Research Objective

The main objective of the study was to find the relationship between job satisfaction and work family conflict among female teachers.

1.2. Hypotheses

Hypotheses were as follows:

H₁: Respondents showing more Job satisfaction will have low work family conflict.

H₂: Permanent female teachers will show less work family conflict as compared to non-permanent female teachers.

H₃: Female teachers with joint family system will show high work family conflict as compared to the female teachers with nuclear family system.

1.3. Methodology

The design of this research is related to after the fact also called as ex post facto design where job satisfaction was taken as independent variable as per its existence. Conflict related to Work-Family is dependent variable. A questionnaire was used to collect the data regarding work family conflict and high and low job satisfaction. The sample was administered on the government and private female teachers of educational institutions. The present study was aimed to explore the relationship between Job Satisfaction and Work Family conflict among Female Teachers. A sample for this study consisting of 300 female teachers (all married) was taken from the educational institution of Islamabad and Rawalpindi without any specific criteria for age. The sample for this study included 300 married

teachers employed by public and private educational institutions. The sample was taken from twin cities of Rawalpindi and Islamabad without any specific criteria. The sampling technique was international and drawn on practical basis. People were selected on the basis inclusion criteria that require being a teacher and a married employee. The design of the research for this survey was intended to ex-post facto design, since the independent variable (job satisfaction) was as is. A brief description of instruments used in present study for the measurement and data collection is given below:

1.4. The Job Satisfaction Scale

The job satisfaction scale is used to measure the levels of satisfaction with the employment. Job satisfaction cc In the adapted study the scale was used. It consists of 18 items. All are rated with Likert's 7-point scale with the options. For the positive items, "1" stands for "strongly agree", "2" for "agree", "3" for "somewhat agree", "4" for "undecided", "5" option is for "somewhat disagree", "6" for "agree" and 7 for "strongly disagree". For the negative items it was reversed.

1.5. Work-family Conflict scale

Work family Conflict scale (WFC) by Ahmad, Saraiti & Martin version II (2003), Singapore was used in this research. This scale consists of 14 items with the rating scale of 5 options. 1 is for "strongly agree" 2 is for "agree" 3 is for "undecided" 4 is for "disagree" and the last one 5 is for: strongly disagree.

1.6. Data Collection

The research was conducted to find out the effects of job satisfaction on marital employed women. Two measures were JSS and WFC were used. After getting the satisfactory reliability of instruments the main study was conducted to analyzed the whole collected data using the instruments. The effects of job satisfaction on the work family conflict were measured by using statistical techniques. The scoring of job satisfaction scale is (score ranging 1 to 7), for positive items scoring was (1,2,3,4,5,6,7) and for negative items scoring was (7,6,5,4,3,2,1). And the Work Family conflict scale has the scoring ranging from 1 to 5, for positive items the scoring was (1,2,3,4,5) and for negative scoring was (5,4,3,2,1).

2. Review of Related Literature

The great deal of research in the area of organization behavior s have explained the determination and correlation of employee's job satisfaction motivation influences of the environmental personal and content factor have also been analyzed through the research studies. As soon as the effect the feelings of employee's feelings and attitudes on productivity has been released. Many remarkable efforts were undertaken to measure the attitude and to chain supervisor to be sensitive to employee's feelings. It was understood that job satisfaction could be improved by job performance where improved performance demand the consideration of one's attitude and feelings. Owing to literature review, emphasis was given on the profession on medicine as the objectives of the present research have been previously described. In this regard almost all resources, of the previous research have been worked out. Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2015) reported that recognition, friendly association, work fitted to vocational level and variety of duties is more important constituting factories in job satisfaction than salary equally for men and women. Sak (2018) found that job satisfaction varies with different kind of occupations. Sahito and Vaisanen (2020) and Butakor, Guo, and Adebajji (2021) studied pay satisfaction, its multidimensional nature and measurement of special issue of job satisfaction they developed a pay satisfaction questionnaire PSQ to assess five dimensions of satisfaction with pay benefits raiser structure, the results provide support for multidimensional hypothesis. Poposki (2011) did a survey concerning job satisfaction in Government service and government industries, found significantly higher level of satisfaction of the government sectors employees.

3. Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Reliability of instruments

Scales	No. Of Items	Alpha Coefficient
Job satisfaction scale	18	0.75
Work family conflict scale	14	0.72

This table shows the alpha coefficient values of both instruments; job satisfaction scale and work family conflict (WFC). The alpha coefficient of the questionnaire measuring job satisfaction was 0.75 and work family conflict contains the alpha coefficient as 0.72, which indicated that both the scales were reliable.

H₁: Respondents showing more Job satisfaction will have low work family conflict.

Table 2: Correlation between work family conflict and job satisfaction

Scales	Job Satisfaction
Work family conflict	-0.81**

Table 2 shows the relationship between Job satisfaction and work family conflict. The result showed that there was a negative correlation between both of them. And also revealed that job satisfaction was negatively influenced by the work family conflict.

H₂: Permanent Female teachers will show less work family conflict as compared to non-permanent female teachers.

Table 3: Job status differences on Job satisfaction and work family conflict

Variables	Permanent n=150		Non-permanent n=150		Df	t	p
	M	SD	M	SD			
Job satisfaction	72.4	18.07	63.9	22.4	298	2.97	0.04
Work family Conflict	57.4	11.5	59.8	10.8	298	2.25	0.06

Table 3 shows the job status between individual having permanent and non-permanent jobs on t-test. The mean of having permanent job on Job satisfaction is 72.4 and SD is 18.07, and on WFC mean is 57.4 and standard deviation is 11.5. The mean of persons having non-permanent job on Job Satisfaction is 63.9 and standard deviation is 22.4, while on WFC the mean of non-permanent jobs is 59.8 and standard deviation is 10.8. The results of t-test were significant.

H₃: Female teachers with joint family system will show high work family conflict as compared to the female teachers with nuclear family system.

Table 4: Family system differences on Job satisfaction and work family conflict

Variables	Joint family n=150		Nuclear family n=150		df	t	p
	M	SD	M	SD			
Job satisfaction	46.62	13.55	55.98	11.98	298	3.61	0.03
Work family Conflict	64.8	21.04	57.05	19.62	298	2.76	0.04

Table 4 shows the difference between individuals having joint and nuclear family systems on t-test. The mean of joint system on Job satisfaction is 46.62 and SD is 13.55, and on WFC mean is 64.8 and standard deviation is 21.04. The mean of persons having nuclear family systems on Job Satisfaction is 55.98 and standard deviation is 11.98, while on WFC the mean is 57.05 and standard deviation is 19.62. The results of t-test were significant.

4. Findings

This research was administered on a sample of 300 married employed women teachers. The sample was drawn from twin cities of Islamabad and Rawalpindi without any specific criteria of age. The sample was purposive. Mean was calculated as the measure of central tendency of the score in normal distribution and standard deviation was calculated for the dispersion of the scores from the mean. Most of the individuals scored around average and scores were distributed normally in the sample. The first hypothesis of the research was that respondent showing more job satisfaction will have less work family conflict. Results indicate that there is a negative relationship between job satisfaction and teachers' work family conflicts. Differences were investigated regarding job satisfaction and work family conflict scale on the basis of family systems to prove the hypotheses of the study those teachers with joint family show less job satisfaction and more conflicts in work and family. The result indicates that job satisfaction is highly influenced by the system having nuclear in the family. Job status was carried out on both scales on Job satisfaction and work family conflict. Teachers with permanent jobs have high job satisfaction as compared to the teachers having status of the non-permanent. Pakistan being an Islamic society with traditional society, women are expected to stay at home and do house work. Their doing job comes in conflict with the values that may cause low teachers' perception.

5. Conclusions and Discussions

The study was aimed to investigate the Job satisfaction and Work family conflict. These scales are the original scales without any translations. All research regarding job satisfaction and work family conflict determined that alpha value of scales more than 0.70 was acceptable. These scales are used to measure the level of job satisfaction and the Work family Conflict among the female married teachers. These scales are valid and reliable which show consistent results

and measure what it claims to be measured. The present study measured the differences on the basis of demographics, for example job status, family system. Moreover, working married women who have nuclear family system have more job satisfaction than the women having joint family system and thus face more difficulties in work and family. The study also finds the relationship between the scales of job satisfaction and work-family conflict. The study indicates the negative correlation between these two scales. When one variable increases, the other decreases. T- tests were also applied to find the differences between the individuals with the job status of permanent and non-permanent job.

5.1. Recommendations

On the basis of findings following recommendations are suggested: Social campaigns may be launched to minimize conflicts due to joint -ofamily system prevailing in Pakistani society. Workshops on conflict resolution may be organized by the continuous professional development sections of education department. The teacher training institute may focus on conflict resolution techniques while preparing future teachers.

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